

Radical initiated Homopolymerization of 2-Octyl Acrylate

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The radical homopolymerization behaviour of higher (longchain) acrylic esters have been investigated to elucidate the effect of the alkyl group in the alcoholic part of the acrylic ester. Benzyl acrylate (AIBN initiator)^{1,4}, methyl², ethyl²⁻⁴, propyl², butyl^{3,4} and n-octyl acrylates⁴ (lauryl peroxide initiator) and ethyl α -hydroxymethyl acrylate⁵ (AIBN initiator) have been polymerized and the kinetics studied. The first such monomer investigated in our laboratory was n-amyl acrylate⁶. We report here the kinetic study of the radical polymerization of 2-octyl acrylate and the properties of the resulting polymers.

Results and Discussion

Homopolymerization of 2-octyl acrylate: The homopolymer was a colourless tacky material. This polymer is soluble in benzene, toluene, hexane, heptane, cyclohexane, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, tetrahydrofuran, ethyl acetate and 1,4-dioxan and insoluble in acetone and alcohol.

It is evident from the ¹H nmr spectra that the polymer is predominantly syndiotactic as was observed in cases of many acrylates initiated by AIBN or benzoyl peroxide⁷. The molecular weight of poly(2-octyl acrylate) was of the order of 15000. From this value it is evident that the higher acrylic esters give polymers of lower molecular weight while their lower members give polymers of higher molecular weight.

Kinetic study: The rate of polymerization increased linearly with the three-half power of the monomer concentration while the rate increased directly with the square-root of the initiator concentration. Raetzsch *et al.*⁸ reported that the rate of polymerization of n-octyl acrylate initiated by lauryl peroxide also increased with the three-half power of the monomer concentration. However the order with respect to the initiator has not been studied.

The rate of polymerization was considerably decreased in the presence of hydroquinone thereby proving the free radical mechanism.

From the study of the effect of temperature on the rate of polymerization, the overall activation energy (E_a) is estimated to be 164.1 kJ mol⁻¹. This is found to be higher than the value determined for n-amyl acrylate⁶. Patra and Mangaraj⁴ calculated the energy of activation for polymerizations of ethyl, n-butyl and benzyl acrylates in the presence of radical initiators and observed that the activation

energy of polymerization increased with the increase in the length of the alcoholic residue.

The molecular weight of the polymer increased with increasing monomer concentration upto 2 M/l beyond which it remained constant as seen from the viscosity data. The molecular weight decreased with increasing initiator concentration in accordance with the mechanism proposed. An increase in temperature decreased the intrinsic viscosity or the molecular weight of the polymer due to termination processes.

Conclusion: The synthesis and characterisation of 2-octyl acrylate and poly(2-octyl acrylate) have been carried out and the kinetics of polymerization studied. The results have been compared with those of shorter chain acrylic esters. The conclusion drawn is that the higher (longchain) acrylic esters undergo radical polymerization less readily than the lower members.

Experimental

Benzene (S.D.) and methanol (SRL) were purified according to standard procedures. AIBN (Trizma Chemicals) was recrystallised twice from chloroform. Hydroquinone (S.D.) was used as received. 2-Octanol (S.D.) was dried overnight with anhydrous potassium carbonate and distilled before use. Methyl acrylate (Wilson Chemical) was used as received.

2-Octyl acrylate was synthesised by transesterification of methyl acrylate with 2-octanol using sulphuric acid as catalyst, (80%) ; ν_{\max} 1720 (C=O), 1630 (C=C) and 980 cm⁻¹ (C=C) ; δ 5.8-6.2 (vinyl-H), 4.9 (methine-H), 1.28 (methylene-H of alcoholic residue) and 0.8799 (CH₃). The purity of the monomer was 97% as determined from its saponification number⁹.

Homopolymerization: A mixture of 2-octyl acrylate (4.2 ml ; 1M), AIBN ($1.218 \times 10^{-5} M$) and benzene (15.8 ml) was degassed by flushing out with nitrogen and heated at 50° for 5 h. The solution was then poured into methanol containing 5% HCl, when a colourless tacky polymer was precipitated in 48% yield.

The molecular weight of the polymer was determined using waters HPLC/GPC instrument at 35° in tetrahydrofuran as solvent at a flow rate of 1 ml per min. A Ultrasijagel 500 Å column with a differential refractometer detector was used. The polymer had the following characteristics : $M_w = 15720$; $M_n = 15374$; $M_w/M_n = 1.022$; ν_{\max} 1730 cm⁻¹

NOTES

(C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 4.9 (methine-H), 1.28 (CH₂ of alcoholic residue), 0.8799 (CH₃) and 2.29 (backbone CH₂).

The viscosity of the polymers was measured using an Ubbelohde viscometer. Solubility of the polymers were tested in different solvents.

Ir spectra (CCl₄) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker CXP spectrometer (90 MHz).

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